

Rockfall susceptibility along communication routes and in urban areas in Italy based on physical and statistical models

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Abstract— Landslide susceptibility, the likelihood of landslide occurrence in different locations of a specific area, can be obtained with many different methods. Here, we aim at comparing two state-of-the-art susceptibility zonations obtained within two such methods, and their predictions at the location of different infrastructure in the whole of Italy. The study considers rockfall landslide type, and susceptibility zonations obtained by a grid-based three-dimensional physically based models and one slope-unit based statistically based model. We first compare the two susceptibility zonations on the whole of Italy, reducing model dependencies by aggregating results of the physical model on the same slope unit zonation as the statistical method. Next, we consider the predictions of both maps restricted to urban areas, railways, and road network. The study shows that the predictions of the two maps are drastically different. We discuss the reasons for such differences, and interpretation of the two versions of rockfalls susceptibility map.

I. INTRODUCTION

Landslides constitute a significant geo hazard inducing financial losses, injuries and fatalities. Significant research attempts appeared over the past twenty years, on predicting the triggering mechanisms for landslides, as well as their spatial and temporal distributions and related consequences. Consequently, several methods for mapping landslide risk, hazard [6-8], and susceptibility have been developed and put into effect in various geographical regions. Assessments of landslide susceptibility take into account the likelihood for a particular location to experience a landslide, based on terrain attributes and past landslide occurrence and it represents the first stage of landslide hazard and risk assessment process.

The recent literature exhibits different approaches for the

spatial zonation of landslide susceptibility. At the opposite sides of the spectrum of possible approaches lie physically based and statistically based methods, which are fundamentally different. Physically based approaches calculate slope stability using well-defined equations, specific of the peculiar landslide type. Statistically based approaches, often mixed with machine learning techniques, establish correlations between several topographic and environmental data and landslide presence. The statistical models usually address a classification problem: given a set of spatial variables and how they are combined to determine whether landslides occur or not, a model should be trained, tested to replicate the desired result, and then applied to data that has not yet been seen.

Past landslide information is useful for both methods, to calibrate model parameters and assess model performance. Other than that, input data may be drastically different. Within the class of statistical and/or machine learning models, many examples exist in the literature; Ref. [9] is a recent critical review on the subject. Examples of physically based methods to obtain landslide susceptibility, applied on large areas as in this work, are probably less abundant in the literature [10, 11].

In particular, rockfalls are one hazardous type of landslide, for their rapidity and destructive potential. They affect infrastructure and transport routes, constituted both by roads [1-3] and railways [4, 5]. This study compares two rockfall susceptibility assessments on the whole of Italy. The first model considered here is an existing statistical zonation [12], calculated across Italy with a slope unit- based spatial granularity [13, 14]. The second is the 3D model STONE, which calculates rockfall trajectories [15-18], which is an inherently grid-based model. In the latter case, we consider here a susceptibility map calculated as an extension to the whole of Italy of the rockfall susceptibility obtained in Ref. [4] for the only railway network in Italy. We first compared the

Figure 1. National scale results for the statistical (GAM) and physical (STONE) maps. Physical model results are averaged in each SU. Both maps depict output transformed by ECDF & classified in equal interval.

two maps on a national scale, and next we compared predictions of both methods restricted to urban areas [18], railways, and road network.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, we compare two state-of-the-art susceptibility zonations, and their predictions at the location of different infrastructure in the whole of Italy, obtained by a physically based method [4] and with a slope unit-based statistical method [10].

The physical model STONE requires a digital elevation model (DEM) of the area, predetermined source locations, and numerical parameters controlling the energy restitution at the location of impacts of boulders with the topography. The model performs full three-dimensional simulations of rockfall trajectories, in the approximation of point-like rock blocks. Maps of friction and energy restitution coefficients can be obtained by re-coding lithological or land-use maps based on data obtained from the literature [1,4]. We used the output, a trajectory count per grid cell produced by the model, to calculate rockfall susceptibility. The most relevant input of the model is a map describing the locations of source cells. Here we used the approach of Ref. [4], in which a simple quantile mode was trained in a relatively small (a few hundreds) number of mapped sources, to provide the probability $P(S)$ of a grid cell with slope angle S to represent a rockfall sources.

The statistical model consists of a Bayesian version of a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) with a multiple intercept for each of the 20 Italian region. This allowed selecting the regions with a poor inventory and discard them in training the GAM, and apply the model to the whole of Italy for eight different landslide

types. Here, we selected the rockfall susceptibility map. The whole procedure was implemented in R-INLA as described in detail in Ref. [10], including fixed (linear) and random (nonlinear) effects from an interpretative standpoint and produced a full prediction equipped with an estimated uncertainty. The statistical assessment considered several predictors, including morphometric parameters: slope, aspect, curvatures, relative slope position and topographic wetness index.

We compared the two results beyond classification performance. In fact, not only are the models very different in implementation and purpose; they also have been trained against disproportionately different landslide data, which makes comparison of performance very difficult, and probably meaningless. For this reason, we first looked at the predictions of the two models at national scale, with slope unit-aggregation level. Next, we consider urban areas, roads, and railways; in each case, we aggregate the two predictions in a different way (road/railway segments and urban areas polygons), in the attempt of reducing as much as possible model dependencies and make results comparable.

At national level, in the statistical model case, spatial aggregation occurred before running the model through predictors aggregated at slope unit level. To run the physical model, instead, the grid input was mandatory, and aggregation was only possible on the result grids. We opted for an average of the trajectory count grids; other aggregation functions are a valid choice. Next, we calculate empirical cumulative density functions (ECDFs) on both models' result, ending up with values ranging from 0 to 1 in both cases. We classify the two maps with equal intervals in ECDFs, corresponding to classes with equal number of slope units. Results of this procedure are in Fig. 1 including results of original GAM.

Table I. Predictions of the two models after aggregation on slope units, at national scale. The values show the total surface area in each susceptibility class, obtained as described in Section II. In the GAM case, each non-null class contains 65,104 slope units, and 44,163 in the STONE case. The null class in the case of STONE model encompasses the following number of slope units in different GAM classes: 55,385 (class 1), 32,522 (2), 11,536 (3), 2,949 (4), 372 (5).

Class	Surface area (STONE) [km ²]	%	Surface area (Original GAM)	%	Surface area (GAM) [km ²]	%
Null	40,889	18.2	-	0	-	0
1	32,045	14.3	18,566	8.3	18,538	8.3
2	32,933	14.7	26,153	11.6	26,15	11.6
3	34,897	15.5	32,989	14.7	32,994	14.7
4	37,543	16.7	47,887	21.3	47,892	21.3
5	46,226	20.6	98,934	44.0	98,907	44.0

We developed another procedure to compare the predictions of the two results restricted to urban areas, railways, and road network. We faced a similar problem as in the comparison at the national scale, except that in this case a mismatch exist with the format of both model results and the target infrastructure. To cope with this issue, we considered the target linear features (roads, railways) as individual segments. We used road and railway data from OpenStreetMap. We calculated ECDFs of the cell-by-cell values of the two model outputs along the segments, assigning to each segment a value between 0 and 1, suitable for classification. Figure 2 shows the classified results.

III. RESULTS

The results portray comparisons of the physical and statistical models at i) national scale, Fig. 1 and Table I, ii) along roads and railway lines and Fig. 2 and Table II.

Table I refers to the national scale comparison. Table I lists the total surface area under each class predicted by the two methods, within the classification scheme described in Section II. Transforming both results by ECDFs, each class in the final classification contains the same number of slope units - 65,104 and 44,163 in the GAM and STONE cases, respectively. One striking difference is that the STONE model predicts a null value about 1/3 of the slope units. This stems from the location of rockfall sources, which are absent in several slope units: consequently, there are no trajectories modeled in the output, in these SUs. The GAM, on the other hand, assigns a result to each SU. We checked that most of the SUs in which STONE predicts a null value are in the “very low” susceptibility class from GAM (55,385 out of 102,764 SUs),

Figure 2. Map showing comparison of roads and railways based on the two methods considered here. Maps obtained aggregating the values of models results along each linear segment (road or railway). The resulting maps were prepared after classification of the calculated ECDF values based on equal interval method

and the number of SUs in the other classes decreases as the class increase.

Figure 2 shows two sample locations where both a road and a railway segment is present, overlapped with result from the GAM and STONE models. The figure does not show the classified results, but the original model output values, to illustrate the aggregation procedure of these values along the linear features. Table II refers to the comparison of model predictions along the road network, about 21,000 km in the OpenStreetMap layer. In this case, we can spot a pattern, as in both models the highest class contains the largest percentage of road segments. As in the national scale comparison, the striking difference is the number of road segments which are assigned a null value by the model STONE, for the same reasons as in the previous case.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The results of the comparison between GAM and STONE results indicate that the maps based on the considered models are drastically different. The observed disparities stem from the

Table II. Susceptibility classes on road network, aggregated on individual road segments using ECDFs, and classified with equal intervals.

Class	Original (GAM)		Statistical (GAM)		Physical (STONE)	
	Total length [km]	%	Total length [km]	%	Total length [km]	%
Null	31,909	59.9	11,119	34.2	23,802	73.4
1	2,184	4.1	2,186	6.7	939	2.8
2	2,882	5.4	2,885	8.8	1,592	4.9
3	3,650	6.9	3,651	11.2	1,658	5.1
4	5,171	9.7	5,172	15.9	1,982	6.1
5	7,408	13.9	7,409	22.8	2,447	7.5

distinct conceptual frameworks and data dependencies of the two methods. We should stress that the comparison strategy adopted here makes use of ECDFs to transform the two model results into comparable ranges. This surely affects the outcome of the comparison, and investigation of additional strategies is in order.

Reconciling the two maps still looks challenging, and these preliminary results suggest complementary use of both methods. The physically based method can easily capture the details of rockfall propagation, strongly dependent of the knowledge of source locations. Even if we applied the model consistently at national scale, increasing its predictive power requires input potentially limiting its use to data-rich locations. In contrast, the statistically based method is more flexible, and suitable for regional-scale mapping. The findings from these comparative analyses offer valuable insights into the strengths and limitations of physically based and statistically based landslide susceptibility models, aiding in the development of improved methodologies for future large-scale hazard assessments.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Research supported by the MUR PRIN Project 'URGERS: URban Geodiversity for a Resilient Environment' (2022M7EP3M_PE10_PRIN2022 - PNRR M4.C2.1.1), funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU (CUP: B53D23007260006).

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